

Project Title	Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative
Project Acronym	digiNEB.eu
Project Number	101083743
Type of project	Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)
Topics	DIGITAL-2021-DEPLOY-01-BAUHAUS
Starting date of Project	1 October 2022
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.digineb.eu

D5.2 - digiNEB.eu Deployment Roadmap, first version

Work Package	WP WP Title
Task	T5.3 Sustainability Roadmap and contribution to future deployment
Lead author	Michela Magas (ICF), Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)
Contributors	
Peer reviewers	Roberto Cavallo (EAAE), Uwe Kies (IW)
Version	V1.1
Due Date	30/09/2023
Submission Date	21/01/2024

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
1.1	23/09/2023	Frank van der Hoeven/TU Delft	Processing
1.2	09/11/2023	Uwe Kies (IW)	Peer Review
1.3	09/11/2023	Roberto Cavallo (EAAE)	Quality Control
1.4	21/01/2023	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Adding conclusions

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CoR	Committee of the Regions
DoA	Description of the Action
EAG	Expert Advisory Group
ECTP	European Construction and Technology Platform
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hubs
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
LMS	Learning Management System
NEB	New European
TWG	Thematic Working Groups

Keywords

New European Bauhaus; Digital Projects; Digital Solutions; Landscape Analysis, Gap Analysis, Road Map.

Disclaimer

digiNEB.eu has received funding from the European Commission's Digital Europe funding programme under Grant Agreement no. 101083743. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Executive Summary

The Roadmap is a strategic action plan to maximize the impact of the digiNEB project. It emphasizes the need for immediate and meaningful actions, ensuring that the initiative evolves as planned in Year 2.

The digiNEB platform aspires to be an open, collaborative co-creation space, fostering training, skills development, and learning within the NEB community while leveraging digital solutions. There is a noticeable cultural difference between the NEB community and IT or engineering communities, which needs to be addressed for effective integration.

Action 1 - WP2: Shifting Towards an Open Repository

This action seeks to transform the digital hub into an open, collaborative co-creation space, offering innovative solutions and promoting interaction among stakeholders. The existing catalog/toolkit approach needs to evolve into an open repository, allowing for content storage and joint development by the active community.

Action 2 - WP2: Aligning with NEB Community

digiNEB will cluster the digital initiatives within the NEB community by organizing workshops to broaden the scope of digital innovation. The aim is to engage key actors in the industry and develop a consolidated NEB community.

Action 3 - WP3: Transitioning to Open Courseware

The E-learning platform provided by digiNEB needs to transform into an open courseware repository to meet the needs of the NEB Academy effectively. It should enable the maintenance of open educational resources and courses by content providers.

Action 4 - WP3: Engaging Regional Ecosystems

The Roadmap aims to collaborate with the Committee of the Regions to establish a regional voucher scheme, involving various EU Regions in creating sustainable solutions using the digiNEB toolkit.

Action 5 - WP4: Continuous Engagement

digiNEB will create a community calendar for regular in-person digiNEB community events. These events aim to foster interaction and engagement among NEB community members, including NEB Fest in Spring 2024.

Action 6 - WP4: Onboarding the EDIH

Efforts will be strengthened to onboard the European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) through a partnership with MADE, the EDIH competence center for Industry 4.0 at the Politecnico di Milano.

Action 7 - WP4: Global Interaction

The digiNEB project will provide a catalogue of tools for the global NEB Fest in 2024, to support partnering with initiatives worldwide and to encourage participation and contribution.

Action 8 - WP4: Open Science and Innovation

To promote community co-creation of sustainable solutions, digiNEB will introduce Open Product Licenses, evolving them with the community in applied scenarios.

Action 9 - WP5: Social Dimension and Accountability

The project will introduce JUST data annotation to ensure responsible research and accountability while respecting privacy and security.

Action 10 - WP5: Building the NEB Academy

Responding to the NEB JRC team's request, digiNEB will put a focus on the NEB Academy, to consolidate a successful launch of the initiative and integrate digital tools relevant to the NEB principles.

Along those actions, the comprehensive Roadmap offers a clear and ambitious plan to guide the digiNEB initiative towards achieving its goals effectively and making a lasting impact within the NEB community.

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
ACTION 1 - WP2: from Digital Hub towards an open, collaborative co-creation space for NEB	5
ACTION 2 – WP2: Alignment of the TWGs with digital project/tools and NEB community	7
ACTION 3 – WP3: Converting the training platform into an open courseware environment	8
ACTION 4 – WP3: Engagement of the regional ecosystems	10
ACTION 5 – WP4: From transferring best practices to community engagement	11
ACTION 6 – WP4: Onboarding of the EDIH	12
ACTION 7 – WP4 Global interaction with the digNEB catalogue of digital solutions and projects.	13
ACTION 8 – WP4: Implement Open Science and Open Innovation practices	14
ACTION 9 – WP5: Implementing the social dimension	15
ACTION 10 – WP5: Building the groundwork for the NEB Academy	16
Conclusions	18

Introduction

The Roadmap is designed to achieve maximum impact from the implementation of the digiNEB Description of the Action (DoA). This Roadmap serves as a guide to our further actions in Year 2 of the project. It outlines a meaningful and effective series of high-impact actions that develop and detail the activities as planned in the DoA.

As such, the Roadmap builds on the ambition of the digiNEB platform as an open, collaborative, co-creation space that is not restricted by claims of proprietary ownership of the uploaded community assets. It establishes a venue for training, skills development, and mutual learning, culminating into the NEB Academy, while mobilising the broader NEB community.

The current initial version of the digiNEB platform lacks the 'click' with the NEB community, so engagement from community members with the website is low. It compels us to acknowledge that visual language, communication, and organizational structures within the NEB community differ a lot from those in IT, ICT or engineering communities. The project needs to bridge these cultural differences and adjust the solutions and methods outlined in the DoA to have a real impact in the NEB community. The aim of this action plan, crafted by the partners TU Delft, ICF, EAAE and IW, is to accomplish this.

ACTION 1 - WP2: from Digital Hub towards an open, collaborative co-creation space for NEB

Pillar 2: Synergising – The digiNEB.eu platform will act as an open, collaborative co-creation space where dialogue and involvement is continually fuelled, encourages synergies and promotes interaction and cooperation among R&I initiatives and stakeholders across Europe. The platform will make it easy to find innovative solutions and allow immediate interaction with the respective solution providers.

[DoA Part B, chapter 1.1.2, p. 8]

The Digital Hub becomes the solid foundation of the DigiNEB project. The project partner Trust-it has been quick to set up an online platform, deploying a proprietary commercial strategy that severely impacted the willingness of the NEB community to participate in the initial releases of the digital platform. It created a bottleneck for broad community participation (see consortium comments to D2.2).

The main approach of the current platform is to develop a catalog/toolkit based on fact sheets (or index cards). It displays information on the projects, tools, and courses from third parties in a uniform predefined manner. However, this approach is not agile enough to adapt to the information provided by third parties. In this way, the platform is far from being effective for the users and doesn't become the primary source of content. It stands merely as an index and faces the risk of no longer being updated, potentially rendering it irrelevant once the project is completed.

The platform provided by the DigiNEB project must shift from a catalog that points to where content can be found online, towards an open repository. This shift would allow content to be stored and accessed by an engaged community utilizing the platform to both retrieve and develop that content.

This entails the online platform, along with the catalogue/toolkit, needing a rework and transformation into an open repository. This transformation will allow project descriptions and fair, open software tools to be stored and developed. In this way the flexibility of the renewed online platform, especially when considering the project's longevity, should hold more importance than a

KPI based solely on the number of documented items added by the consortium itself.

Summary of the action:

Rework and transform existing online platform, including catalogue/toolkit, into an open and more interactive repository.

ACTION 2 – WP2: Alignment of the TWGs with digital project/tools and NEB community

[...] by analysing, mapping and clustering relevant R&I projects coming from different funding programmes such as H2020 & HE, CEF Telecom, Creative Europe, Structural Funds projects etc. DigiNEB.eu will create a platform for continuous engagement, organising regular, structured concertation efforts as well as workshops and events to reinforce and engage a consolidated community with an eye towards engaging key actors in industry.

[DoA Part B, Objective 1, p.9]

The project kicked off with a preliminary proposal for so-called Technical Working Groups (TWGs). However, the work on the catalogue has shed more light on how to engage with the NEB community. The landscape analysis, based on the content of the catalogue, resulted in a clustering of digital initiatives. This clustering will be used as a basis for identifying five 'discussion working groups' within the NEB community. Workshops will be organized around these clusters:

1. Parametric/Computational design (with EAAE/CAADfutures/ACE)
2. Education, training, skills development (with EAAE)
3. Community engagement (with cities, regions, civic organizations)
4. BIM/Digital Twins (with ECTP)
5. Biobased sector as an integrator (with Innovawood/ACE)

The aim of these workshops is to identify innovations that did not surface during the initial tool/project identification process, and to broaden the potential field of digital innovation beyond the core 'creative' focus of the NEB community.

Onboarding of TWG participants is to be implemented via the Expert Advisory Group (EAG) that has proven to be very active (see events hosted by EAG members above). The topics will reflect the broadest community interests.

DELIVERABLES:

D2.5 Landscape report and gap analysis - final (M24)

ACTION 3 – WP3: Converting the training platform into an open courseware environment

[DoA Part B, Objective 4, p.11]

The E-learning platform that was provided by Trust-IT to the partners in July 2023 follows a similar structure to the digital toolkit: a catalogue based on fact sheets (or index cards) compiled by the project partners. It was complemented with a Moodle open-source Learning Management System (LMS).

Currently, anyone wishing to visit the E-learning platform must register and log in before any further action, even to access content that is publicly accessible on external websites.

In the meantime, the E-learning platform is intended to serve as the foundation for the NEB Academy. Initial conversations with content producers for the NEB Academy highlight the necessity for an agile approach. Tailor-made solutions are required for the content to be shared and developed using the platform. Consequently, it's evident that a predefined, inflexible structure will not effectively support and serve the NEB community.

Considering the points mentioned above, the E-learning platform must transition into an open courseware repository where open educational resources and full courses can be uploaded and maintained by the content providers. This adaptation ensures that the platform effectively caters to the needs of their activities and allows for easy content management, thereby keeping the material up-to-date and relevant.

We would like to emphasize that our primary focus is to establish a platform that can organically expand through codesign with the NEB community members, tailored to meet the precise needs of its users. This takes precedence over adhering strictly to a fixed quantitative KPI, factsheets or courses to be added in the coming 12 months.

DELIVERABLES:

D2.4 digiNEB platform Rel. 3.0 (M18)

D3.2 Training programme and knowledge sharing (M20)

D3.3 Transferring innovation best practices (M23)

ACTION 4 – WP3: Engagement of the regional ecosystems

“[...]pursue a community-development approach by aligning with the NEB Lighthouse and NEB Lab initiatives, and by envisaging a co-ordinated set of communications and marketing actions to support the engagement of all stakeholders, encompassing designers, architects, artists, managers, business actors including start-ups/SMEs in particular from the building, mobility and health sector, and citizens for co-creation activities.”

[DoA Part B, Objective 3, p.11]

digiNEB has supported to develop a proposal developed by ICF with the European Committee of the Regions (CoR) for a regional voucher scheme that has recently been approved by the European Parliament.

The progress of this work is reported in greater detail in D3.1. digiNEB is developing a **Regional Innovation Model** and related **Handbook** based on best practice of NEB community engagement reported in the first digiNEB webinar (an early draft was submitted in the Annex of D3.1).

In order to engage NEB communities across Europe in creating sustainable solutions based on regional needs, the project is tasked with onboarding Regional Champions, with considerable engagement of the EU Regions achieved via the NEB Lighthouse projects (30+ Regions). The digiNEB toolkit of compiled technologies is planned to be used by the regional communities for innovative sustainable solutions.

While the strategy and its detailed steps are clearly outlined in D3.1, the challenges associated with the underperforming online platform (refer to previous action points) are currently impeding the project partners from progressing with the task's implementation. The expectation is that these challenges will be alleviated with the renewed online platform.

DELIVERABLES:

D3.4 Champions network, national and regional adoption (M23)

ACTION 5 – WP4: From transferring best practices to community engagement

“[...] multi-stakeholder and citizen engagement and dialogue at local, regional and EU level ensuring full representation of the ecosystem, offering multiple engagement mechanisms such as events, digital communications, one-on-one engagement, opportunities for partnerships/MoUs.

[DoA Part B, 3.1.1 , p.29]

This Roadmap works towards an open platform for continuous engagement. While the engagement efforts have been remarkable thus far, the Trust-IT’s budgetary constraints limit in-person events to €2400 per event, acting as a restriction on the project’s ability to expand its reach.

Regular, structured engagement efforts have already begun with the successful co-located 3-day event at CERN, that galvanised all NEB Lighthouses, NEB Lab, CERN Green Village and Smart Communities projects (reported extensively in D3.1). This has been followed with offers by individual members of the newly created multidisciplinary digiNEB community to host digiNEB community in-person events on a regular basis.

A follow-up community in-person event was co-located by the NEB Lab project Bauhaus Goes South in Zagreb, organised by digiNEB EAG member Mia Roth in Croatia on the 20-21 September, linked to the biggest sustainability conference in the region.

Further co-located community events are being planned with various community members such as the EAG Member Martin Luce (TUM) and the NEBourhoods NEB Lighthouse project in Neuperlach, ZHAW Winterthur, InnoRenew in Izola, Global Innovation Gathering, the SenseLab at TU Delft and the MADE EDIH in Milano (see Action 6). A community calendar will be implemented for effective planning of regular digiNEB community events, that will culminate with the global NEB Fest in Spring 2024.

DELIVERABLES:

D2.4 digiNEB platform Rel. 3.0 (M18)

D4.2 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report – intermediate (M18)

D4.3 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report – final (M24)

ACTION 6 – WP4: Onboarding of the EDIH

“[...] support and deeply engage with the EDIH to increase capacities for investing, R&I, training and skills development for digital innovation and uptake. [...] to connect and partner-up with the EDIH for synergies of actions and network building, integration of data platforms, dissemination, innovation and broad exploitation of results together with SMEs and start-ups linked to both communities.

[DoA Part B, 1.3 , p.16]

The aim to onboard the European Digital Innovation Hubs is commencing through a collaboration with MADE, the EDIH competence centre for Industry 4.0 at the Politecnico di Milano.

DELIVERABLES:

D4.2 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - intermediate (M18)

D4.3 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - final (M24)

ACTION 7 – WP4 Global interaction with the digNEB catalogue of digital solutions and projects.

“[...] participation to 3rd party events [...] aimed at optimising resources to solidly positioning the project inside the international digital & NEB ecosystems.”

[DoA Part B, 3.1.2.7 , p.38]

DigiNEB has been incorporated into the initial plan for the **NEB Fest 2024**:

The festival will be decentralized, transcending the core event at Brussels. Thus, it will have a strategy to partner with initiatives Europe-wide and globally, opening our program to satellite events all over the world built with the help of our NEB community. Satellite labs worldwide could run the entire week, culminating into the festival. **It should provide a NEB Fest Toolkit**, with tools that enable NEB partners, friends, and others to participate and contribute.

digiNEB has been asked to provide and present the toolkit for this global event in Spring 2024. Leading up to this event, digiNEB will identify cutting-edge technologies and startups to integrate into the toolkit (for example, [Lepei.ai](#) a Deep Learning-based service that recognises 3D and BIM objects from video photo or point cloud). The aim is to disseminate this information to the NEB community.

DELIVERABLES:

D2.4 digiNEB platform Rel. 3.0 (M18)

D4.2 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - intermediate (M18)

D4.3 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - final (M24)

ACTION 8 – WP4: Implement Open Science and Open Innovation practices

“[...]Enable a NEB digital Hub through which innovative designs, concepts and ideas can be shared, modified, developed and reused as open data/open design/open science/open source, open standards and technical specifications”

[DoA Part B, 1.3.1 , p.16]

Proprietary systems introduced by Trust-IT hindered active participation of the other consortium members in building the digital platform during the first 12 months of the project (see consortium comments to D2.4).

To stimulate community co-creation of sustainable solutions, digiNEB will introduce 8 **Open Product Licences** and evolve them with the community in applied scenarios. Open Product Licences were originally evolved with support from CERN and National Government funding, building on CERN's Open Hardware Licences to cater for IoT and Smart Communities (openproduct.cc).

DELIVERABLES:

D2.4 digiNEB platform Rel. 3.0 (M18)

D4.2 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - intermediate (M18)

D4.3 Stakeholder engagement plan, adoption and monitoring report - final (M24)

ACTION 9 – WP5: Implementing the social dimension

“[...] To facilitate FAIR data use, data visualisation will be used to extensively condense information and present it effectively in the digital Observatory.”

[DoA Part B, 1.3.1 , p.17]

To fulfil the social and ethical dimension, accountability and impacts on privacy and security, the project will introduce **JUST data annotation**. This approach was introduced as part of the strategy for the expansion of EOSC, and is recommended in the creative industries AI report for DG CNECT. JUST creates a complementary system to FAIR data that encourages responsible research. It introduces data annotation by the data creator, owner or researcher, that aims to be Judicious, Unbiased, Safe and Transparent. See "Study for the Expansion of EOSC"; EOSC SRIA; and the creative industries AI report¹.

The JUST data annotation will be implemented in the NEB academy.

DELIVERABLES:

D5.3 digiNEB deployment roadmap (M24)

¹ Magas, M., 2022 contribution to European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Izsak, K., Terrier, A., Kreutzer, S., et al. Opportunities and challenges of artificial intelligence technologies for the cultural and creative sectors. Publications Office of the European Union.

ACTION 10 – WP5: Building the groundwork for the NEB Academy

*“[...]provide **efficient training programmes for co-creation between different categories of stakeholders** by enabling effective knowledge transfer between digital research and NEB communities and providing them with the necessary knowledge, allowing them to upskill and become long-term beneficiaries of the project’s outcomes. The training programme will be delivered in both online and live environments, by alignment with NEB Lighthouses, NEB Labs and DIH events”*

[DoA Part B, 1.1.3, Objective 4 , p.11]

The initial landscape and gap analysis, drawn from a collection of 250+ digital innovations and projects primarily searched and compiled by TU Delft, has enabled us to conduct a preliminary gap analysis. This analysis forms the basis for the issues we aim to address through the Roadmap.

Funding

Within the NEB community, there is evident digital tool development by architects, designers, and civic organization. However very few, if any, of these developed tools declare support from EU-funded projects. The predominantly micro-enterprise structure in architectural design sector appears to have limited alignment with EU programming, resulting in inadequate engagement with the extensive, complex, and mostly large project calls within the Horizon programs. digiNEB will conceive a concept for funding calls that matches the NEB community. This could potentially consider cascade funding and take its cue from the FIWARE accelerators that ran under FP7, where community embedded consortia were made responsible to setup grant schemes for specific niches of digital development.

Accessibility

While most developers of parametric design tools and participatory tools for citizens have adopted the principle of open (source) software, the majority of tools produced with funding from EU projects are either not easily accessible or not accessible at all. digiNEB seeks to provide an open digital space where digital projects can be archived and further developed without any barriers.

Findability

The field shows numerous sites providing overviews of digital tools pertinent to the NEB community, but these resources are scattered across various online locations. Finding and effectively utilizing them is quite challenging and tedious. digiNEB intends to leverage the NEB banner to unite several of these aggregators under a single digital roof.

Integration

The NEB is founded on three key principles: aesthetics, sustainability, and inclusion. While tools aligned with each of these principles have been identified, integrating these tools to encompass all three principles poses a significant challenge. Currently, only a few good examples of such comprehensive integration have been discovered.

NEB Academy

The [NEB Academy](#) is a flagship initiative of the European Year of Skills. Its launch was announced by the EC President Ursula herself at the ‘NEB Into the Woods’ conference on 24 Nov 2022, hosted by the Nordic Bauhaus initiative in Espoo, Finland ([press statement & video](#)).

At the request of the EC-JRC, digiNEB incorporated the NEB Academy topic and integrated it as its own TWG, moderated by IW. This TWG includes several EAG members who have been consistently conducting meetings to develop the initial concept of NEB Academy.

ICF, IW and EAG members participated jointly in the launch event of the *NEB Academy Pioneer Hub* (NEBAP) facilitated by the University of Primorska, in Izola, Slovenia, on 22-23 March 2023. This collective workshop, involving 25 experts, was utilized to further refine the NEB Academy concept ([news info UoP, W4B](#)).

DELIVERABLES:

D5.3 digiNEB deployment roadmap (M24)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the digiNEB Roadmap outlines a comprehensive strategy for the project's Year 2, addressing challenges and emphasizing key actions across various work packages. The primary focus is on transforming the digiNEB platform into an open, collaborative co-creation space that resonates with the NEB community. The roadmap introduces essential actions, such as reworking the online platform into an interactive repository, aligning Technical Working Groups with digital projects and the NEB community, converting the training platform into an open courseware environment, and engaging regional ecosystems.

The roadmap also emphasizes the importance of community engagement, both locally and globally, through various events, workshops, and collaborations. Actions such as onboarding the European Digital Innovation Hubs, participating in third-party events, and implementing Open Science and Open Innovation practices underscore the project's commitment to fostering a vibrant and inclusive NEB community.

Furthermore, the roadmap addresses the social and ethical dimensions by introducing the concept of JUST data annotation, ensuring responsible research practices within the NEB Academy. The conclusion highlights the groundwork laid for the NEB Academy, aiming to provide efficient training programs and bridge the gap between digital research and the NEB communities.

Overall, the digiNEB Roadmap serves as a strategic guide to achieving maximum impact, fostering collaboration, and creating a sustainable and inclusive digital innovation ecosystem within the NEB community.